

Detecting Spiral Text Lines in Aramaic Incantation Bowls

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Abstract. Due to irregular spacing, character overlap, and varying orientations, text line detection is especially challenging for unconstrained handwritten and historical documents. These complexities make traditional methods, designed for straight lines, insufficient for detecting spiral text lines from Aramaic incantation bowls used in Sasanian Mesopotamia between the 4th and 7th centuries CE. We introduce a novel learning-based method for extracting spiral text lines inscribed on the surfaces of Aramaic incantation bowls. Our model utilizes an encoder-decoder architecture while leveraging connections among corresponding layers, similar to UNet. It combines high-level and low-level features, enabling precise localization and segmenting spiral text lines.

Furthermore, we propose a novel metric to evaluate the dissimilarity between predicted and ground-truth lines. Inspired by the Intersection-over-Union (IoU) metric, We compare our model with the state-of-the-art methods and show that our approach outperforms these methods in terms of the introduced metric.

Keywords: Text Line Detection · Spiral Text Lines · Archaeological Images · Incantation Bowls · UNet

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Fig. 1. The performance of our approach compared to two leading methods for detecting spiral text lines on Aramaic incantation bowls. The first and the second images show an input patch and its corresponding ground truth, respectively. The third image shows the results of applying FCN8 [2], where the detecting lines appear in yellow blobs. The result of running Seamformer [18] is presented in the fourth image, where the detecting lines are in green blobs. Seamformer detects blobs and applies post-processing to connect them into polylines. The last image shows the results of our model.

1 Introduction

Text Line Detection (TLD) is a fundamental task in the field of historical documents. It remains an active research area in historical document image analysis and handwritten texts, particularly those with irregular spacing, overlapping characters, and diverse orientations. The growing interest is due to the significant impact of text line detection on various tasks, such as text recognition and document categorization. However, TLD can be highly challenging due to the unconstrained nature of handwritten documents, which often feature complex and variable text line layouts, degradation, multiple handwriting styles, scripts, fonts, and other irregularities. These challenges complicate accurately detecting and extracting text lines, requiring sophisticated techniques to handle such documents’ diverse and intricate patterns.

During the last decades, numerous methods have been proposed for text line detection and extraction in handwritten documents [2, 5, 7, 10, 16]. Existing methods for text line detection, such as [2, 18] achieve promising results for horizontal, vertical, and slightly curved lines, they often struggle with more complex patterns like spiral lines, as shown in Figure 1.

In this paper, we introduce a novel learning-based method for extracting spiral text lines inscribed on the surfaces of Aramaic incantation bowls. These text lines often exhibit perspective distortion in the bowl images. Our model utilizes an encoder-decoder architecture while incorporating connections among corresponding layers, similar to UNet. It combines high-level and low-level features, enabling precise localization and segmentation of text lines. We compare the proposed approach with the state-of-the-art methods and show that it achieved superior accuracy scores.

Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

1. We present a new dataset that includes images of Aramaic incantation bowls and artifacts used in Sasanian Mesopotamia between the 4th and 7th centuries CE [12], and their corresponding ground truth spiral text line annota-

tions, as shown in Figure 5. These bowls present a unique set of challenges for TLD since they bear inscriptions in various script styles arranged in spiral patterns, reflecting the magical nature of their contents. The images were downloaded from the British Museum collection, and our research team performed the annotation using a specially developed GUI-based annotator, which is freely available to the research community.⁵

2. We develop a novel approach for extracting spiral text lines from Aramaic incantation bowls. Our learning model adopts the encoder-decoder methodology. In addition, we explored various encoder backbones, such as ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-101, and ResNet-152, as well as advanced residual architectures, such as ResNeXt and WideResNet.
3. We propose two new metrics to evaluate the performance of the models and overcome the sensitivity of Intersection Over Union (IoU) for small and thin objects, named Fuzzy IoU.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 overviews recent studies and methodologies for text line extraction and detection. Section 3 presents the new dataset and the annotations facilitated by the GUI developed by our team. In Section 4, we detail our approach for text-line detection, which utilizes the L-UNet architecture. We present the results of our experiments in Section 5, providing quantitative metrics and qualitative analysis of the detection outputs. Finally, in Section 6, we conclude with a summary of our findings.

2 Related Work

Text line detection and extraction have long been recognized as a preprocessing step in analyzing handwritten document images. Various methods have been proposed to address this task, primarily focusing on detecting and segmenting horizontal or straight text lines [4, 11, 17, 18]. However, the challenge escalates when dealing with historical documents characterized by irregularities and intricate layouts, such as those found in Aramaic incantation bowls featuring spiral text lines (see Fig. 4). In this section, we review existing methodologies for text line detection and extraction in historical documents, highlighting their relevance and limitations in addressing the unique challenges posed by spiral text patterns.

Droby et al. [4] utilize Mask R-CNN for holistic text line extraction. By training a Mask R-CNN model on document patches, this method effectively detects and segments text lines, achieving state-of-the-art results on well-known datasets of historical documents.

Alaql [1] proposes an approach based on local connectivity maps for text line extraction in historical documents. By utilizing dynamic steerable directional filters, this method effectively estimates the orientation angles of text lines, facilitating accurate segmentation. Furthermore, it introduces adaptive local connectivity maps to address document complexity and low-quality challenges. Ra-

⁵ <https://github.com/SaeedYNaa/GUI-For-TLE-data-labeling>

Fig. 2. An illustrative diagram of the UNet architecture, renowned for its skip connections facilitating high-resolution feature maps reconstruction, alongside its contracting (encoder) and expanding (decoder) pathways designed for efficient image segmentation.

hal et al. [13] presents an approach based on background and foreground information for text line extraction in graphical documents. This method, inspired by the concepts of local connectivity maps, effectively segments text lines while addressing document quality and complexity challenges.

Recent developments in deep learning-based document segmentation have shown promising results in simultaneously addressing various document processing tasks. Oliveira et al. [17] introduce dhSegment, a generic deep-learning approach designed to handle multiple document processing tasks, including page extraction, baseline extraction, layout analysis, and extraction of illustrations and photographs. By employing a CNN-based pixel-wise predictor coupled with task-dependent post-processing blocks, dhSegment offers a flexible and efficient solution capable of handling the diversity of historical document series.

Ronneberge et al. [15] present a language-independent global method for automatic text line extraction from historical document images. The proposed approach computes an energy map of the text image and determines seams that pass across and between text lines. Two algorithms are developed based on this concept, catering to binary and grayscale document images. The algorithms utilize different techniques, such as component extraction and distance transform, to segment text lines accurately. A benchmark dataset containing historical document images with various challenges, including different languages, is also introduced for evaluation purposes.

Next, we provide a detailed overview of fully convolutional deep learning methods categorized as linear-based and UNet-based approaches for text line detection. The approaches represented by architectures such as *FCN* [2] and *Fast and Lightweight* [11] are considered linear-based methods, while *dhSegments* [17] and *L-UNet* [14] architectures exhibit of UNet-based architecture. Each of these architectures, belonging to both categories, offers unique advantages tailored to various aspects of text line detection, including capturing contextual information and mapping low-resolution feature maps.

2.1 Linear-Based Fully Convolutional Network

This section overviews the linear-based, fully convolutional *FCN* and *Fast and Lightweight* networks that we utilized for this study.

FCN architecture. The Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) architecture, depicted in Figure 3, is based on the FCN proposed for semantic segmentation [2,9]. We experimented with two configurations, FCN8 and FCN32, which comprise an encoder and a decoder. These configurations were selected for their success in page layout analysis of handwritten documents [2]. The encoder downsamples the input image, enabling the filters to capture broader information with a larger receptive field. The decoder combines the final layer of the encoder with lower layers containing finer information and then upsamples the combined layer back to the input size using transpose convolution, where upsampling with a factor f involves applying a convolution filter with a stride equal to $\frac{1}{f}$.

The main difference between FCN8 and FCN32 lies in their levels of up-sampling. While FCN32 directly upsamples the final layer of the encoder to the input size, FCN8 integrates the final layer with lower layers and subsequently upsamples the combined layer back to the input size.

Fast and Lightweight architecture. The proposed network architecture [11] is based on previous research [19], but with modifications to enhance text line detection. It utilizes standard convolutions instead of separable convolutions in early layers and adjusts certain layers while maintaining robust performance. The compact design ensures efficiency with a few trainable parameters and is called from herein as *FastSmall*. The ReLU activation function was employed throughout the network, with sigmoid used in the final layer. An expanded model with small residual connections and extra layers is proposed, referred to here as *FastLarge*.

2.2 UNet-Based Fully Convolutional Network

This section overviews the U-Net-based fully convolutional networks explored in this study.

The **L-UNet** [14] is UNet-based architecture for page layout semantic segmentation and text line segmentation of historical document images. This architecture draws inspiration from the UNet model, particularly Doc-UFCN [3], for its utilization of dilated convolutions, as depicted in Figure 2. A notable aspect of this architecture is the reduced number of filters, especially in the encoder blocks operating at lower resolutions. In contrast to other architectures that typically double the number of filters at each block level, the L-U-Net architecture argues for a consistent number of filters across all levels, contending that it effectively captures the characteristics necessary for document layout analysis.

The **dhSegment architecture** comprises two main components: an encoding path and a decoding path [17]. Following the ResNet-50 [6] architecture, the encoding path includes five convolutional blocks and progressively reduces the size of feature maps through each step, halving the size at each step. Pretrained weights from ImageNet are utilized to enhance robustness and generalization.

Fig. 3. A Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) architecture. In this example, $32\times$ up-sampling is applied to obtain output of the same size as the input, referred as **FCN32**.

The decoding path comprises five blocks and a final convolutional layer, assigning a class to each pixel. Each deconvolutional step involves upscaling the previous block’s feature map, concatenating it with the corresponding encoding feature map, and applying a 3×3 convolutional layer followed by a ReLU activation. Finally, the output prediction has the same size as the input image, and the number of feature channels constitutes the desired number of classes.

3 Dataset

This paper introduces a new dataset to train and evaluate our approach. It contains images of Aramaic incantation bowls downloaded from the British Museum collection. These artifacts, dating back to the Sasanian era (4th to 7th-centuries CE), bear inscriptions characterized by a mixture of Jewish, Zoroastrian, and pagan elements, often arranged in spiral patterns surrounding symbolic images, as shown in Figure 4. The inscriptions typically consist of incantations, prayers, and curses, reflecting the syncretic religious practices prevalent.

To facilitate the extraction of spiral text lines from the bowl images, we annotate the dataset using a specially developed annotation tool that includes an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI). It enables marking the location of text lines within the bowl images.

We generate a polyline list and a mask for each image in the dataset. The polyline list indicates the center of the text lines, and the mask image delineates the text line regions using white spiral lines against a black background. This annotated dataset is of great value for developing and evaluating methodologies aimed at extracting text lines from spiral patterns.

Figure 5 illustrates the data labeling and clarifies converting the raw image into a labeled data tuple containing the original image and the corresponding labeled mask.

4 Method

We present a novel learning-based approach for extracting spiral text lines inscribed on Aramaic incantation bowls’ surfaces. These text lines are also subject to perspective distortion as we process images of these bowls. Our model follows

Fig. 4. Samples of the Aramaic incantation bowls images.

Fig. 5. The image on the left shows the original bowl image and the annotation (overlay) as it is displayed in our annotation tool. The two images on the right show the original image and the annotated mask, displayed in greyscale, which delimits the lines of text in the original image.

the encoder-decoder methodology, which includes Fully Convolutional Networks and U-Net.

The encoder-decoder architecture consists of an encoder that compresses the input image into a lower-dimensional representation through a series of convolutional layers and downsampling operations, capturing essential features while reducing spatial dimensions. The decoder reconstructs the compressed representation into the original spatial dimensions using upsampling operations and convolutional layers, restoring image details and resolution.

UNet, a type of encoder-decoder architecture specifically designed for image segmentation tasks, features a symmetric structure with a contracting path (encoder) and an expansive path (decoder), incorporating skip connections between corresponding layers to retain fine-grained spatial information, as shown in Figure 2.

Our model is used for pixel-wise predictions, classifying each pixel in the input image into categories such as background or text. It incorporates connections among corresponding layers, similar to U-Net, and combines high-level and low-

level features, enabling precise localization and segmentation of the text lines, even with perspective distortions. Our model adopts the ResNeXt as a backbone for encoding.

The encoding path starts with the initial layer, including the 7×7 convolutional layer, followed by BatchNorm, ReLU activation, and Max pooling; then, it consists of 4 layers whose content varies according to the backbone. Each layer includes multiple convolutional layers, batch norms, and activation functions but excludes max pooling layers. It is structured to progressively reduce the spatial dimensions of the input while increasing the depth (number of filters), allowing the network to capture complex features at multiple scales. These features typically include edges, textures, and complex patterns essential for accurately detecting and extracting text lines.

The decoding path comprises five blocks and a final convolutional layer, which assigns a class to each pixel. During each step in the decoding path, the feature map from the previous block is upsampled, concatenated with the corresponding feature map from the encoding path, and processed through a 3×3 convolutional layer followed by a ReLU activation. This concatenation ensures that spatial information from the encoding path is preserved and utilized effectively. The output prediction retains the same dimensions as the input image, with the number of channels corresponding to the desired number of classes, allowing for precise segmentation of the spiral text lines from the background and other elements in the bowls.

4.1 Fuzzy IOU

Intersection over Union (IoU) is an evaluation metric extensively employed across computer vision tasks to assess the precision of object detection algorithms. It was initially introduced to compare bounding boxes, but it has been applied to evaluate mask segments, particularly in semantic and instance segmentation tasks. Its effectiveness dwindles when applied to small objects such as text lines, primarily due to their diminutive size. Though seemingly insignificant at first glance, factors like subtle translations, rotations, or resizing of predicted text lines can unexpectedly wield a disproportionate influence on resulting IoU scores. These minor alterations may not appear critical to the overall outcome, and they might be deemed acceptable in the results, as shown in Figure 6. However, when considering IoU values, they fail to reflect this lack of criticality, potentially leading to significant distortions in assessing model performance.

To address the limitation of IoU, we augment the thickness of text line annotations (the polylines) to diminish the metric’s vulnerability to minor alterations like small translations and adjustments. This augmentation enhances the evaluation process’s resilience.

We propose two approaches for augmenting the thickness of text line annotations (polylines). The first one avoids penalization for small translations and is considered fully correct results. It extends the annotation boundaries by t pixels on each side, making the lines more thicker, as shown in Figure 7b. This is achieved by applying a kernel of size $t \times t$ using morphological dilation operations.

Fig. 6. Results of text line detection. The red and blue lines represent the model predictions and the ground truth, respectively. Despite the noticeable visual disparity, the difference between the blue (ground truth) and red (prediction) lines is not critical. In (a), there is an average translation of 5 pixels in the x-direction, whereas in (b), the translation is 5 pixels in the y-direction.

The second aims to handle minor translations and adjustments based on a fuzzy evaluation. It involves augmenting the polylines with weights that vary as we move away from the center, as depicted in Figure 7.c. These weights are calculated based on the Distance Transform with Euclidean distance, normalized between 1 at the center of the text line and 0 at the outer edges.

Fig. 7. (a) Ground Truth of Text Lines: Displays the true representation of text lines. (b) Expansion Using Dilation: Shows dilation-based expansion, with minor alterations considered correct. Thickness increases by t pixels on each side. (c) Weighted Results: Illustrates weighted augmentation of text lines, with weights varying gradually from 1 at the center to 0 at the edges, calculated using Distance Transform with Euclidean distance normalization.

Let's define P as the set of predicted text lines and G as the set of ground truth text lines (polylines). Additionally, G_t denotes the ground truth after augmentation with t pixels using the dilation operator, where t represents the ex-

pansion parameter. We calculate the fuzzy Intersection over Union (IoU_t) as the intersection of P with G_t , divided by the union of P and G , as shown in Equation 1.

$$IoU_t = \frac{P \cap G_t}{P \cup G} \quad (1)$$

G_d represents the ground truth after augmentation with the Distance Transform and using Euclidean distance. Similar to Equation 1, we define the IoU metric (IoU_d) to be the intersection of P with G_d , divided by the union of P and G . This approach comprehensively assesses text line detection performance under different augmentation techniques.

$$IoU_d = \frac{P \cap G_d}{P \cup G} \quad (2)$$

The modified IoU metrics, IoU_t and IoU_d , offer a nuanced assessment of text line detection systems by accounting for text line thickness augmentations variations. They evaluate how accurately detected text lines align with the ground truth under the specified augmentation technique. Our choice of the thickening augmentation technique aims to balance sensitivity to variations in text line predictions with resilience against minor perturbations. This enhances the stability and reliability of model evaluations, providing clearer insights into its performance in text line detection tasks.

5 Experimental Evaluation

We have experimentally evaluated our model and compared its performance with the state-of-the-art methods. Initially, we employed linear FCN models, including FCN8, FCN32, FastSmall and FastLarge [11] to detect spiral text lines. However, these models struggled to grasp the complexity of spiral text line detection, leading to unsatisfactory results, as shown in Fig. 1.

Therefore, our evaluation focused on U-Net-based models, which can effectively capture the low-level and semantic features. The L-UNet, which is a lightweight yet robust model equipped with dilatation convolution blocks, exhibits notable improvements over linear models, attributing its success to the integration of residual/skip connections between encoder and decoder blocks, facilitating the fusion of features essential for accurate text line detection.

The dhSegment, an UNet-based model fortified with residual dilatation convolution blocks and adopts ResNet50 as its encoder, demonstrates superior capabilities compared to L-UNet. Still it does not output accurate results compared to our model, as shown in Table 1.

We explore various UNet architecture encoding path backbones, including ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-101, and ResNet-152. In addition, we examined advanced residual techniques such as WideResNet and compared their performance with our model (See Section 4).

Fig. 8. The result of the patching techniques applied to the original image, where the leftmost panel illustrates the annotated image alongside the bounding box encapsulating the annotated region and three overlapping sliding windows $\{w_i\}_{i=1}^3$ applied to the image. Morphological operations, specifically dilation, ensure a slight margin between the bounding box and the outermost spiral line. This operation increases the annotation lines' thickness, creating space between the original annotation lines (text) and the bounding box covering the largest contours of the dilated annotation image. The right part illustrates the resulting extracted patch images P_{w_i} and their corresponding annotation patch labels L_{w_i} .

5.1 Dataset Preparation

The dataset preparation involves extracting patches of size 512×512 that capture a significant portion of a bowl image. We ensure that each patch contains multiple lines of text to provide enough spatial information for the model to learn the intricate patterns and variations present in the text lines.

To generate patches, we apply a sliding window to the original images using a stride of 256 pixel in both X and Y directions, creating an overlap among consecutive windows. This approach ensures comprehensive coverage of the bowl images while maintaining contextual information across adjacent patches.

We avoid generating patches that do not include text lines by utilizing the annotated text lines to guide the calculation of tight bounding boxes (include text) and applying the sliding window within these boxes. Similarly, the annotated data (the corresponding masks) undergoes the same bounding process, ensuring that each patch of the bowl image corresponds to its respective patch label as illustrated in Figure 8.

The original bowl images are split into three sets with a ratio of 70%, 15%, and 15% for the train, validation, and test subsets, respectively. We allow an overlap of bowls between the train and validation sets.

5.2 Training

Throughout the training process, for all the models, we utilize the Adam optimizer [8], alongside a batch size of 8 for a duration of 30 epochs, training each model from scratch with a learning rate of 0.002. The training used patches of size 512×512 , where 0 denoted the background and 1 denoted the text line region. Additionally, binary Cross Entropy was employed as the loss function to minimize the loss during the training.

5.3 Results and Analysis

The overlapping patches of size 512×512 are extracted from the test set images during the inference stage. We assessed the results using the two approaches outlined in Section 4.1. For the IoU_t metric, we varied the expansion parameter t , considering values of 2, 3, 4, and 5 as detailed in Table 1. These variations are labeled as IoU_2 , IoU_3 , IoU_4 , and IoU_5 , respectively. Additionally, we conducted another evaluation to calculate the models’ performance using the IoU_d metric, as presented in Table 1. .

Model	IoU_2	IoU_3	IoU_4	IoU_5	IoU_d
FCN32	17.97	19.40	20.84	22.22	19.12
FCN8	17.92	19.35	20.77	22.15	12.86
L-UNet	70.40	72.81	74.4	74.74	51.12
ResNet101	88.45	90.75	92.04	91.48	71.18
ResNet18	72.38	74.44	75.78	76.80	58.54
ResNet34	82.93	84.33	85.25	85.60	67.18
dhsegment	74.93	76.24	77.94	78.37	59.88
Ours w/ResNext101	89.95	90.41	91.39	91.53	75.24
Ours w/ResNext50	89.81	91.20	92.22	92.41	74.69
WideResNet101	89.44	91.09	92.11	92.34	73.86
WideResNet50	87.35	88.42	89.18	89.30	72.88

Table 1. Model Results: Performance metrics of different models using IoU_t and IoU_d techniques.

Table 1 shows varying performance metrics across different models and evaluation techniques. For instance, models FCN32 and FCN8 exhibit lower scores than the ResNet101, ResNet18, ResNet34, and ResNet50 models. Among these, our method with ResNext101_32x8d and ResNext50_32x4d as the encoding backbone, as shown in Figure 9, stand out with the highest scores among other models, respectively, for the IoU_t and IoU_d metrics.

ResNext models demonstrate superior performance to WideResNet and standard ResNet due to their enhanced architecture, incorporating a more efficient feature extraction and representation learning design. This enhanced architecture allows ResNext models to capture more diverse and complex patterns within the data, leading to improved accuracy and performance in various tasks.

Fig. 9. Series of images showing the ground truth alongside predictions from two different architectures in our experiment: *ResNext50*, and *ResNext101*.

The lower values of IoU_d compared to the IoU_t reflect the differences in the way the two methods handle augmentation of text line annotations (polylines). While dilation uniformly expands the predicted text lines, the distance transform method assigns varying weights to pixels based on their distance from the text line center. This nuanced approach may result in some predicted pixels being assigned lower weights, particularly those farther away from the boundary.

6 Conclusions

In this study, we have introduced a novel method for detecting and extracting spiral text lines by utilizing an encoder-decoder similar to UNet architecture, which combines high-level and low-level features for precise segmentation. To facilitate the experiments, we created a GUI-based annotator to annotate the dataset, easily creating plenty of annotated datasets for the learning process. In addition, we have shown that training linear-based FCN and U-Net-based architectures for detecting spiral text lines on Aramaic incantation bowls is possible. We also showed that the UNet-based models show superior performance compared to linear-based models.

We have demonstrated that the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric has limitations when used for spiral line detection. To address these limitations, we introduced the fuzzy IoU metric that avoids penalization for small translations between the ground truth and the predicted polylines by applying morphological operation and calculating the distance transform map of the ground truth polylines.

The scope of future work focuses on exploring the applicability of our approach to other datasets that include highly curved or circular text lines.

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